

PROCESSING OF ELASTOMERS USING REFRIGERANT

Products with a combination of polymer and metal components are widely used in industry. These include cable products, high-pressure hoses, metal-plastic pipes, polymer parts with embedded metal elements, etc. The main difficulty faced by recyclers when disposing of such products is the separation of insulating material from metal (steel, aluminum, aluminum, etc.). With existing technologies in the process of shredding is simultaneously destroyed to small fractions of both the polymer coating and the metal element, which leads to an increase in the power consumption of the shredder, as well as complicates the further separation of the necessary components. This disadvantage can be eliminated by using a vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber. The possibility of using a refrigerant in it in combination with high-frequency percussive application of a metered load to the product allows to destroy the polymer component without destroying the metal element. Significant effect is obtained when processing products with multilayer polymer coating, in particular cable products.

Such a technological line contains a number of sequentially located and interconnected modules, the number of modules corresponds to the number of layers of polymer coating. The technological line includes: drum 1 with the source material 2; module of the first stage of material layer removal 3, including cooling chamber 4, vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber 5, hopper for receiving the crushed layer of material 6 and container 7; module of the final stage of material layer removal 8 with cooling chamber 4, vibrating crusher 5, hopper 6 and container 7; receiving drum 9.

The method of processing multilayer material using the technological line is carried out as follows.

Based on physical and mechanical properties of the material of layers or on the basis of theoretical and experimental studies, determine and set rational parameters of cooling and force impact for each of the layers. According to the obtained data, the equipment of the module of each stage of removal of a separate layer of material is adjusted (for example: time and temperature of cooling, frequency of jaw oscillation, number of blows, etc.). When the initial material passes the technological line in each of the modules (3,8) the crushing of the corresponding layer of material is carried out, unloaded into the containers 7 located under the crushers. The material not intended for crushing falls into the receiving drum 9.

As an example, let us consider the process of cable processing according to the proposed method. The cable 2 from the drum 1 is fed into the cooling chamber 4 of the module 3 of the first stage of insulation coating removal. Depending on the required set cooling temperature, the refrigerant may be (in particular) liquid nitrogen or air flow of a turbo-cooling machine. In the cooling chamber 4, the upper layer of the insulating coating of the cable 2 is brought to a state of embrittlement, while the plastic properties of the underlying layers remain unchanged. From the cooling chamber 4, the cable 2 enters a vibrating jaw crusher 5 with an inclined crushing chamber, where, in the crushing process, only the upper (cooled) layer of the insulating coating is destroyed, while the underlying

layers remain intact. From the vibrating crusher 5 of the module 3 of the first stage of removal, the crushed layer of insulation coating is unloaded through the hopper 6 into the container 7, and the cable enters the cooling chamber 5 of the next module of removal of insulation coating. Here a new layer (which is already the top layer) of insulating coating is brought to the embrittlement state under the parameters of the predetermined temperature regime corresponding only to this layer. The number of modules, cooling and crushing cycles depends on the required number of destructible material layers, and each cycle is carried out under the parameters of temperature and force regimes characteristic only for it.

In the module 8 the cooled cable passes through the crusher 5 of the final stage of removal, the crushed layer of insulation coating, through the hopper 6, falls into the container 7, and the cleaned current-carrying conductor is wound on the drum 9. This method allows to remove a certain number of layers of insulation coating, leaving, for example, with insulation only the current-carrying conductor.

Such a step-by-step method of processing multilayer material and the device for its realization eliminates mixing of crushed material with different physical and mechanical properties, increases the speed of material cooling, reduces refrigerant consumption and cheapens the processing process.